

A study to assess the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women at selected area in Madurai District.

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Abstract

This study is carried out to assess the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women, with the following objectives to assess the level of knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy, to find out the correlation between the level of knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy, to find the association between pre-test levels of knowledge and attitude with the selected demographic variables. Research hypothesis were formulated to find out the significance. Review of the literature was done and organized based on studies related prevention of teenage pregnancy.

The conceptual framework for this study was derived from Luding Von Bertalanffy (1995) General System Theory. Reliability was established by Cronbach's Alpha Method. The findings were revealed that, in experimental and control group in pretest respectively 29(96.70%) and 27(90%) of them had inadequate level of knowledge, also in post-test majority 20(66.70%) of them had adequate knowledge in experimental group and 18(60%) of them had inadequate level of knowledge in control group, there is significant improvement on posttest in experimental group than the control group due to the effect of the intervention.

Both in experimental and control group inpretest 29(96.70%) and 28(93.30%) of them had moderately favourable attitude respectively, and inposttest in experimental group majority 28(93.30.%) of them had favourable level of attitude due to an intervention and only 2(6.70%) of them had favourable level of attitude.

The current findings suggests that Video Assisted Teaching Programme is an effective teaching in improving the knowledge and develop desirable attitudes regarding teenage pregnancy.

Keywords: Assess, Effectiveness, Video Assisted Teaching Programme, Knowledge, Attitude, Teenage pregnancy, Fortunetellers community women (A person who assume to have magic powers and who tells people what will happen to people in the future).

INTRODUCTION

Women are the most powerful and are fragile in our society. Women are the back bone of her family in all aspects of life. These women face so many hardships and still struggles to raise up herself including the society. ⁽¹⁾

Teenage mothers were more likely to develop premature rupture of membrane (PRM), obstetrical complications such as preterm labour (20.9%) and gestational hypertension (12.3%), mild to severe preeclampsia (10.3%), eclampsia (3.7%), intrauterine infection (5.7%) and also higher IMR and MMR rates, which also keep our nation in a state of underdevelopment. STP or like similar interventions are to lower the teenage pregnancy rates could be implemented in school, including rural and urban area. ⁽²⁾

Statement of the Problem

A study to assess the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women at selected area in Madurai District.

Objectives

1. To assess the level of knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.
2. To assess the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.
3. To find out the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.
4. To find the association between pre and post-test levels of knowledge and attitude with the selected demographic variables regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.

HYPOTHESIS

H1: The mean post-test score is significantly higher than the mean pre-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.

H2: There is a significant correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.

H3: There is a significant association between the pre-test and post-test knowledge and attitude with the selected demographic variables regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women.

ASSUMPTIONS

- The level of knowledge is enhanced after the Video Assisted Teaching Programme.
- The Video Assisted Teaching Programme creates a positive attitude towards the prevention of teenage pregnancy.
- The knowledge and attitude of the Fortunetellers community women may influence on prevention of teenage pregnancy.

DELIMITATIONS

1. Fortunetellers Community Women were only included in this study, the results may not be generalized to other women.
2. Data were collected only through face to face interview from the Fortunetellers Community Women having female child.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design chosen for this study was quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test control group design.

Population

In this study, the samples were from Fortunetellers community-60, in which 30 samples in control and 30-samples in experimental group. Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used.

Criteria for Sample Selection

Inclusion Criteria

- Women who are from Fortunetellers Community and aged between 15 to 50 years.
- Having a female child.
- Women who did not undergo similar study

Exclusion Criteria

- Fortunetellers’ community women with psychiatric problems.
- Women who are not willing to participate in the study.

Development and Description of the Tool and Validity of the Tool

Content validity of the tool was established. Reliability of the structured MCQ questionnaire ($r' = 0.81$) were established by Cronbach’s alpha co-efficient method and modified five point Likert’s Scale ($r' = 0.85$) by test and retest method. It was found to be highly reliable.

Pilot Study

Pilot study was conducted, significant difference was found between pre and posttest level of knowledge and attitude in experimental group than the control group. Video Assisted Teaching Programme is effective regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy. In control group there is no significant changes between pre and posttest level of knowledge and attitude.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The investigator selected 60(30 experimental and 30 control group) Fortunetellers community women, who fulfilled the inclusion criteria by purposive sampling technique. In experimental group pretest was conducted, Video Assisted Teaching Programme was administered for 45 minutes to 1 hour, on 8th day posttest was conducted with the same assessment tool.

In control group, pretest was conducted, on 8th day posttest was conducted with the same assessment tool. After the posttest Video Assisted Teaching Programme was administered for 45 minutes to 1 hour.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Majority (76.7%) and (90%) of them were between the age of 26 to 35, respectively in control and experimental group.

Fig. 2. Pretest and post- test of the level of attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community Women in experimental and control group.

Tab.1: Correlation between knowledge and attitude in experimental group.

Assessment	Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	'r' Value	'p' Value
Pretest	Knowledge	5.78	1.29	0.166	0.204 NS
	Attitude	27.47	2.75		
Posttest	Knowledge	11.42	4.29	0.779	0.000** HS
	Attitude	35.10	8.34		

*p<0.05 significant, ** p<0.01 & ***p<0.001 highly significant.

Tab.1 reveals the correlation between knowledge and attitude, in experimental group pretest, It shows that, there is a significant positive correlation between knowledge and attitude. The result indicates that there is an improvement in the post-test mean score in the experimental group after the introduction of the Video Assisted Teaching Programme. Video Assisted Teaching Programme is effective in improving the knowledge and attitude regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy in experimental group.

There is a significant association between pretest level of knowledge with demographic variables such as age at menarche 9.31(df =2) p'valve 0.010 and monthly income 30(df =2) p'valve 0.000. There is no significant association between the pretest level of knowledge with demographic variables such as age in years, type of family, age at marriage and educational status.

There is no statistical significant association posttest level of knowledge with demographic variables such as age in years, type of family, educational status and personal habits.

There is no significant association between pretest level of attitude with demographic variables such as age in years, type of family, age at menarche, age at marriage, educational status and monthly income. There is no significant association in posttest level of attitude with demographic variables such as age in years, type of family, age at menarche, educational status, monthly income and personal habits.

Delimitation

- The study was delimited to the selected Fortunetellers Community. Therefore, the wider generalization was not possible.

Implications

- The findings of the study had implications on the field of nursing education, nursing practice, nursing administration and nursing research.

Nursing Education

- To foster good knowledge and attitude towards teenage pregnancy during nursing conferences, workshops and seminars to update their expertise and Nurses working in a variety of healthcare settings can upgrade their knowledge and skills through in-service education.

Community Nursing Practice

- The finding of this study will create an awareness to Fortunetellers community women about the complications of teenage pregnancy.
- The Video Assisted Teaching Programme brings the positive attitude towards teenage pregnancy.
- To find the girls who are at risk, surveys might be undertaken.
- To treat and prevent teenage pregnancy, screening camps can be organized and early detection can be carried out through the school system.
- The community health nurse can examine students on a regular basis to spot the high risk groups.
- The community health nurse needs to be knowledgeable about many areas of teenage pregnancy education and prevention strategies.
- The school health nurse might be guided by the community health nurse in conducting a Programme to raise awareness of teenage pregnancy.
- By using the right audiovisual tools, a health education Programme on teenage pregnancy can be delivered to the community as mass health education.
- To educate the local population about teenage pregnancy, self-instructional materials can be distributed.

Nursing Administration

The goal of the current study is to assist community health administrators in developing a strategic plan and addressing the health needs of adolescent girls.

- Administrators in the public and private sectors should take the initiative to update risk groups awareness of teenage pregnancy.
- The administrator can be motivated to prevention of teenage pregnancy.
- For community-based nurses, the administrator conducts conferences, workshops and seminars.
- The administration needs to assist the staff to organize programmes on teenage pregnancy prevention.

Nursing Research

- The study can serve as a useful source of information for future researchers.
- This study serves as a foundation for further investigation into the ideas of knowledge and attitude towards teenage pregnancy.
- The study's findings may inspire teenage girls and mothers of a family to pursue healthy lifestyles.

Conclusions

The current findings suggests that Video Assisted Teaching Programme is an effective teaching method and it can be administered easily which in turn will improve the knowledge and develop desirable attitude which has been acquired from the teaching.

This study will improve the knowledge and attitude of the Fortunetellers Community Women regarding prevention of teenage pregnancy. This study will prevent teenage pregnancy among Fortunetellers Community. It creates a positive perspective on adult marriage also having healthy generations in future

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations were:

- A similar study can be conducted among another vulnerable female group.
- A comparative approach can be used to know the level of knowledge and attitude on prevention of teenage pregnancy between regions.
- The study can be replicated with a large number of participates for generalization.
- A similar study can be conducted among school girls attitude on prevention of teenage pregnancy between regions.

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